

Bridging Educational Voids: The Emergence and Significance of Sociology in Somali Higher Education

Zakarie Abdi Bade

Sociology Department, Ankara Yildirim Beyazıt University, Turkey

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the absence of sociology as an academic subject within Somali higher education, delve into the history of higher education in Somalis, examine the primary themes of sociological debates in the country, and explore potential prospects for offering sociology as a field of study in Somali universities. By employing a Qualitative Descriptive Review methodology, the study thoroughly reviews and thematically analyzes a range of literature, such as academic papers, historical documents, and policy papers, instead of gathering primary data. This method is selected to provide a comprehensive account of the obstacles and opportunities in incorporating sociology into the curricula of Somali universities. Somali higher education, which commenced with the establishment of Somali National University following independence, has experienced a turbulent history. Initially, the only operational university during the military regime until 1991, the fall of the military government resulted in several decades of conflict and instability. Despite these challenges, several universities have been active over the past two decades, but they have largely overlooked sociology, resulting in a notable deficiency in the social sciences. The study demonstrates that the lack of sociology in Somali universities represents a significant oversight, given the subject's potential to contribute to understanding and addressing social issues in a post-conflict society. In conclusion, the paper advocates for the urgent need to integrate sociology into the curricula of Somali universities, arguing that doing so would not only bridge an existing academic gap but also equip future generations with essential tools to analyze and positively contribute to the rebuilding and development of Somali society.

Keywords: *Sociology, Somalia, Somali universities.*

Suggested citation: Bade, Z.A. (2024). Bridging Educational Voids: The Emergence and Significance of Sociology in Somali Higher Education. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(1), 66-77. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(1).06

Introduction

Sociology is one of the primary disciplines in social science and deals with learning about human life and their interactions. In the last two centuries, social changes significantly caused by the industrial revolution brought many unexpected changes to society. The transformation of society from agrarians in rural areas to modern industrialized life in urban caused many problems— overpopulation, poor health,

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

alienation, crimes and so on. Thus, understanding those problems empirically became necessary. Classical sociologists who experienced social changes at that moment employed sociology as a scientific discipline to study and analyze those social events. Nevertheless, sociology had only been studying in Western Europe and America. It later spread to other parts of the world.

Generally, education has been part of colonization policy in Africa where colonizers designed it to facilitate their interest in colonizing countries. Somali universities have not been providing sociology as a study field since Somalia's independence and formation of Somali higher education. Universities have an essential function to the society and train well informed intellectual for society. Sociology remains vital to understand social problems; unfortunately, it is a missing gap in Somali universities.

Therefore, this article discusses the sociological gap in Somali universities. Hence, for understanding sociology as a separate discipline of study, this article discusses the development of sociology as a separate field of study, and the main contributors of sociology. It also examines the background of Somali education and sociological arguments in Somali studies. Finally, this article shows Somali universities' potential opportunities in developing sociology as a study field and its expected contributions to studying and solving the prolonged Somali problems.

Methodology

This article utilizes a Qualitative Descriptive Review methodology, which entails an extensive review and thematic analysis of existing literature to investigate the development and current state of sociology as an academic discipline within Somali universities. Rather than collecting primary data through questionnaires or interviews, this methodology relies primarily on a thorough analysis of academic papers, historical documents, policy papers, and relevant educational texts. This approach is particularly suited to the study's objective of constructing a comprehensive narrative that captures both the historical evolution and the contemporary landscape of sociology in Somali higher education. By systematically categorizing and analyzing the data into emergent themes, the study provides a nuanced understanding of the challenges, achievements, and potential opportunities for sociology in this unique academic and cultural context. The decision to forego primary data collection is deliberate, as the study focuses on providing a synthesized overview of existing knowledge rather than generating new empirical data. However, this approach also comes with inherent limitations, such as the reliance on secondary sources, which may not fully capture the most current on-the-ground realities. Nonetheless, the Qualitative Descriptive Review serves as a robust framework for this exploratory and descriptive study, enabling a holistic and informed perspective on the subject matter.

The Evolutionary Path: Tracing the Roots of Sociology in Academic Spheres

Sociology is stated to as the study of societies, and how they interact. The enormous changes in society that occurred in dramatic social times paved the way to the modern world. Sociology emerged in the 19th century as a discipline in a reaction to modernism. The problems and uncertainties ignited by modernity, including rationalization, bureaucratization, industrialization, and urbanization. The dissimilarity

concerning the gap between traditional and modern steered the Industrial Revolution in the 19th century and produced the term 'modernity'. Marshall & Scott (1998) notes that “the Industrial Revolution refers to the rapid changes in areas such as culture, industry, politics, technology, science, and communication, which took place in the latter half of the eighteenth century to the first half of the nineteenth century” (Marshall & Scott, 1998).

Generally, during the Industrial revolution people experienced enormous transformation in their ways of lives in terms of culture, science, technology and politics, which the Industrial Revolution impacted. As a result of steady scientific and technological progress brought by the Industrial Revolution, production methods continuously developed (Royce, 2015, p. 7). In the ways of production, enhanced machines were utilized for more enhanced and efficient production. The development of machine production was a big part of the story.

The Industrial Revolution was not merely an innovative transformation; it was likewise, and all the more critically, a social upheaval (Royce, 2015, p. 8). It brought about the disintegration of a conventional lifestyle and an extreme change in society's fundamental association and functions. In a traditional form of life, individuals transcendentally lived in rural settlements, and their essential method of making a living was as agricultural work. In this sort of form, the family was the focal unit of production but, with industrialization and the developing population, society preferred to migrate to urban areas.

Mobility and migration from rural to urban cities paved the way for the momentous transformation of people's lives. The migration to metropolitan cities generated a lot of unprecedented challenges to society. According to Royce (2015), the recently shown up city tenant experienced an unforgiving and alien social climate: swarmed and unsanitary lodging, air and water contamination, deficient public offices and administrations, new and severe working conditions, and metropolitan social connections of a distinctively generic and market-intervened structure. The establishment of a prevailing industrial workplace, the factory, is one of the most significant developments accompanying industrialization processes. The factory system's emergency completely renovated the lives of working people and those of labour. The story of factory productivity laid down a division between work and family life created a separate sphere between the public and the private in the household. It centralized production, gathering workers under the same roof, placing them under their employers' direct supervision, thereby enabling capitalists to control and monitor the labour process more effectively. It also caused thousands of children and women to become labourers working under brutal conditions.

In the wake of industrialization, Auguste Comte, Karl Marx, Herbert Spencer, Emile Durkheim, and Max Weber were the leading sociologists that argued for a scheme of sympathetic sociological change. All of the classical sociologists had different theories but contributed to sociology as a discipline. The theorists tried to understand and explain how the changes caused by industrialization might impact society. The craving to comprehend and investigate such dramatic changes gave early sociologists an impetus to create theories identifying with labor division, bureaucracy, and capitalism and their consequences for social change in the public arena (Marshall & Scott, 1998).

Pioneers and Pillars: Influential Figures Shaping Sociological Thought

Auguste Comte

Familiar as the founder of sociology, Auguste Comte, who first used the term sociology, tried to study and analyze social order and structure. Comte's primary interest lay in the social order and worked hard to comprehend what creates the social order and how it influences change. Thus, Comte laid the cornerstone of his evolutionary theory. Commonly known as the law of three stages, Comte argued that human society went through three intellectual stages. As indicated by Comte, not merely does the world experience this process, yet gatherings, social orders, sciences, people, and even personalities experience similar three phases (Ritzer, 2011, p. 16).

The first stage is theological, in which the focal thought framework accepted strict figures, and otherworldly powers are the base of everything showed after individuals. Specifically, the social and actual world is viewed as delivered by God (Ritzer, 2011, p. 17). The second stage is metaphysical, in which the explanations were more philosophical. In this stage, people believed that non-concrete powers like nature rather than religious persons describe everything entirely. Finally, Positivist is the final stage. In this stage, the scientific approach is the main phenomena to explain the social world. People now tended to give up the search for fundamental causes (God and nature) and concentrated instead on observation of the social and physical world in the search for the laws governing them (Ritzer, 2011, p. 18). Comte also labelled the word positivism; it implies that the scientific method should be the necessary tool for sociological studies.

Herbert Spencer

Herbert Spencer argued that no one should guide social reform and that society merely grows from inferior forms to a superior and civilized arrangement. Spencer believed that the most talented persons mature to the top and untalented or the least skilled die out in this fashion. Spencer named this idea "survival of the fittest", and Spencer's social order theories became known as social Darwinism. Spencer contributed to the development of sociology as a separate discipline. His book, the study of Sociology, maybe the most coherent of every one of his works, had a huge deal and likely accomplished more to excite revenue in the subject than some other distribution previously or since (Cooley, 1920).

Emile Durkheim

For the first time, sociology as a separate discipline and science was developed by Emile Durkheim. Durkheim understood that the idea of sociology had been in French philosophy in the 19th century. He endeavored to set the idea of sociology into a field of study, an all-around created separate field of study. He recognized the roots of sociology in the ancient philosophers – such as Plato and Aristotle – more proximate sources in French philosophers such as Montesquieu and Condorcet (Ritzer, 2011, p. 76). Nevertheless, what makes Durkheim the founder of sociology, a separate discipline is that prior philosophers never went far enough and did not find an entirely new field – Sociology. Before Durkheim, there had been no school of sociology, professors or even university departments. Rawls, 2007 and Jones, 2000 noted that "Durkheim legitimized sociology in France, and his work ultimately became a dominant force in the development of sociology in general and in sociological theory in particular" (Ritzer, 2011, p. 19).

In his effort to separate sociology from philosophy, Durkheim contended that sociology should go toward empirical research. Generally, two main themes fall under the work of Emile Durkheim. The first is the priority of the social over the individual, and the second is the idea that society can be studied scientifically.

Durkheim created functionalism, which keeps up social and cultural solidarity through collaborations (Ferrante-Wallace, 2013). The division of labour is the most famous work of Durkheim, which discusses how economic regulation maintains social order. Durkheim strongly believed that the study of social fact is the primary function of sociology. He argued that individuals' behaviour, feelings and thoughts fall external to the individual consciousness. This concept is the cornerstone of *solidarity*, a social fact that binds society together. Durkheim showed that the solidarity altered meaningfully with the increase of industrialization. He insisted on the need to analyze and explain and a mechanism that styled the solidarity. In his works, abstract social facts gained more attention. He came to focus on perhaps the ultimate form of nonmaterial social fact – religion – in his last major work, *The Elementary Forms of Religious life* (Ritzer, 2011, p. 20).

In this work, Durkheim argued that religion and society were single and similar. He argues that a manner society justifies itself in the way of nonmaterial social fact is religion. These books and other essential works helped carve out a distinctive domain for sociology in the academic world of turn-of-the-century France, and they earned a scholarly journal devoted to sociology, *L'année sociologique* (Besnard, 1983).

Karl Marx

Karl Marx, a German sociologist, philosopher and revolutionist, was an influential individual to sociology. In the field of sociology, Marx's theories are used to investigate society throughout economic systems. As indicated by Ritzer (2011), Marx believed that social change was driven by strife and that it molded the methods for production, for example, land, labor, factory, and tools. He understood this system ignited a clash between the classes, the exploiting and exploited. The Industrial Revolution's consequences created a division of conflicting classes known as the bourgeoisie and the proletariat. Marx recognized the bourgeoisie as the owners of production means, whereas; the proletariat is the labourers who vend their time and skills to the bourgeoisie.

Marx's works crucially contributed to sociology. Marx committed his life to understanding the causes and outcomes of the inequality and disparity, which he associated with a weak spot in the association of production (Ferrante-Wallace, 2013)

Marx's theories innovated a sociological perspective known as conflict. Marx argued that capitalists did not care about human needs and necessitated people to sell their time and energy for products they could not have enough money to purchase. His philosophy and the timing of his writings helped early sociologists in the development of social theories and scientific approaches (Hammond et al., 2015, p. 7). Marx accepted that if the economic system were administered by individuals who had society's wellbeing on the most fundamental level rather than the individuals who had been persuaded by benefit, there would be more available abundance. It very well may be conveyed among society as per need. Thus, Marx proposed a revolution to overthrow the capitalist system and substitute it with communism.

Max Weber

Max Weber is one of the key founders of sociology. He was a very intelligent person who strongly influenced the development of sociology and taught some of the other early sociologists of his day (Hammond et al., 2015, p. 8). To balance the revolutionary ideas of Karl Marx, Weber learnt economics and religion. In Weber's work, *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*, he writes that the Protestant (particularly Calvinist) ethic influenced people to work in the secular world (Ritzer, 2011). Weber believed that capitalism came into existence because of the protestants' activities – the foundation of businesses, interest in trade, and capital assortment for investment aims.

He also studied bureaucracies and defined Ideal Type as the abstract description of social phenomena by which actual social phenomena may be compared (Hammond et al., 2015, p. 7). Ideal Types are given as hypothetical examples, and we can compare current economic systems to them (Hammond et al., 2015, p. 7). Weber was interested in social actions and mentioned their types: traditional, affectional, value-rational and instrumental.

Weber also contemplated bureaucracy and imagined that administration was the industrial society's disagreement as he saw it move from a value-oriented association and activity to an objective-oriented situated association and action (Jacoby, 1976). Weber accepted, heavily influenced by legitimization and bureaucratization, that society would be caught in an "iron pen" under severe guidelines from which there would be no way out (Jacoby, 1976). As mentioned above, the sociologists facilitated understanding society through sociological investigation and highlighted the importance of sociology in social science. Thus, sociology's acceptance as a separate discipline of the study came into existence.

Educational Genesis: the Historical Landscape of Learning in Somalis

Higher education in Africa mainly dates back to the independence era. Jowi et al., (2013), noted “right from independence, African founding leaders clearly recognized the important role that high-quality higher education could play in building the new nations” (Jowi et al., 2013). Consequently, since its commencement, Africa's advanced education area has seen the formative part as being central to its central goal, reason, and command (Sawyer, 2004). 1960, known as an African Year, was crucial to Africa as many countries gaining independence from the colonials and founding independent nations. The part of the African 14 universities being developed was firmly stressed, prompting the foundation of public colleges in a large portion of the recently autonomous nations (Jowi et al., 2013).

The education in Somalis had based on Islamic studies and the Arabic language. Together with the Somali traders, seamen, soldiers, and religious pilgrims, the spread of Islam and the Arabic language got some sorts of education in different forms. Small Somali communities at the coast were introduced to a mixture of western and Islamic education long before the arrival of European colonizers in Somalia (Diriye, 2019). Unlike other African countries, colonials faced challenges in implementing formal education in Somali communities. The Somalis believed that colonials have missionaries to spread Christianity and feared their children would shift to Christianity. But, colonial education in Somalia was, as elsewhere in Africa, designed and pragmatically implemented for the imperial powers' administrative and low-level

technical needs (Abdi, 1998). With that impact, as Rodney (1974) calls attention to, the pilgrim educational system 'was to prepare Africans to help staff the nearby organization at the positions, and to staff the capitalist firms which implied the support of not many Africans in the mastery and misuse of the mainland all in all' (Abdi, 1998).

1972 was a landmark achievement of Somali education for the adoption of Latin script for Somali language writing. As a written language, Somali carried the Somalization of state capacities and managerial areas, trailed by its continuous usage as the medium of instruction in education (Pestalozza, 1974). The writing of the Somali language coupled with a mass literacy campaign in the rural areas (Somalia: a country report, 1982) was also responsible for sharply increasing the rate of literacy, which immediately went from a dismal 5% to an estimated 55% (Laitin & Samatar, 1987) in the mid-1970s (Abdi, 1998). The 1974/1975 literacy campaign programmes physically involved the mobilization of 100,000 students and civil servants, who were sent 'to the countryside to live, learn and study with the nation's large nomadic population for a period of six months or more' (Sheik-Abdi, 1981).

Higher education in Somalia was founded in 1954 under the Italian Trust Territory following the foundation of Somali National University, which gained its official status university status in 1969. Somali National University was the first and only university during the military regime since 1991. With pre-state collapse student figures of 4650, Somali National University established itself as a full edged institution of higher learning with 11 faculties: law, economics, agriculture, education, veterinary medicine, medicine, industrial chemistry, geology, languages, journalism, and engineering (Taylor et al., 1993). Despite the increasing interest in sociology at the time, sociology has been missing in Somali universities.

The Societal Mosaic: Examining Key Sociological Themes in Somali Context

Like many countries in Africa, Somali people had suffered under various colonial powers, including Britain, Italy, France and Ethiopia. Colonial powers introduced formal education in most of Africa, yet, there had been some type of education that allowed for the colonized people to study. Education under colonials always served for the implementation of colonial interests. In spite of the enormous advances made in Africanist scholarship since the early 1970s, Somali studies remained locked in traditional social anthropology (Samatar, 2006). To understand the social structure—culture, specifically, clan lies in the heart of Somali life. Thus, Somali studies' central debates deal with the Somali culture, where the tribe is the main focus. Therefore, Somali studies' debates centre on anthropology, where foreign scholars focused on and Somali scholars analyzed and criticized it.

Although sociology as a field of study remains absent in Somali universities since the Somali higher education foundation, some Somali scholars studied in sociology and investigated Somalis sociologically. Most of those Somali scholars learned sociology outside the country, mainly in Western countries. According to the literature (Behr, 2018; Eno & Kusow, 2014; Ingiriis, 2020; Kusow, 2004; Samatar, 2006; Bade, 2020; Bade & Hared, 2021), Somalia's leading sociological arguments refer to the Somali identity. A sociological approach to the Somali clan system and its functions extensively highlights the complexity of the evolving phenomenon of Somaliness and the variety of criteria for qualification to that identity (Eno, 2008, p. 288). There are conflicting arguments on Somali identity; what is the genealogy of Somalis? What

factors make the Somaliness? As a mark of evolving power and Islamic civilization rooted in Arabia influenced the primitive Somalis to assume Arabness genealogically.

In the mind of the Somali nomad of that time, Arabness was superior compared to the African identity in his neighborhood (Eno, 2008, p. 287). On the other hand, there is a belief that Somalis belong to the Cushitic communities in Eastern Africa. In this sense, Somalis speak a language with family members of Cushitic languages. Physical characteristics also contribute to this argument.

According to Kusow (2004), there is a contested narrative between two significant Somaliness paradigms: one deals with lineage roots, and the other is territorial. This perspective starts from the ontological assumption that the fundamental problems that inform much of the social crisis in Africa, and Somalia in particular, result from "contested narratives" (Kusow, 2004). The first paradigm is based on state-sponsored idealistic images and founding myths that have no practical use to the everyday realities of the people (Kusow, 2004). This paradigm establishes a border on the identity of Somaliness, focusing on lineage primacies. The second paradigm (the territorial narrative) constructs the social boundary of Somaliness not on lineage/Maandeeq priorities, but rather on economic, moral, and territorial priorities (Kusow, 2004). Those paradigms mentioned above conflict with each other and resume to be significant in identifying the Somali identity.

Migration is another crucial sociological argument in Somalis. Somalis had a long history of migration deep in their culture. They are pastoralists who move from somewhere to another, looking for pasture and water for their livestock. However, the majority of exiles left their country as refugees at the outbreak of the civil wars: starting in late 1988 in the northern part of the country (currently Somaliland), and from 1991 in the rest of the country when the collapse of Siyad Bare's regime resulted in a devastating civil war (Moret, Baglioni, & Efiñayí-mäder, 2006). Following the collapse of the central government, Somalis resettled in many countries and got a significant share of the world migrants. Somali refugees are the fourth-largest population globally, and the largest black migrants entered Canada in 1988-1966 (Abdulle et al., 2012; Ifrah Mohamud Magan, 2019). The trends of Somali migrants depend on the situation in the country. In 1990, there were 478.3 thousand Somali immigrants worldwide compared to 20.7 thousand in 2005 and 52.1 thousand in 2019. This data shows that in 1990, 6.6% of international migrants were Somalis, the number decreased to 0.2% in 2005, and it has again increased to 0.3% in 2019 (UN DESA, 2019).

The literature on Somalis' migration shows that Somalis face different challenges during their stages of movement, resettling, and integration (Abdisalan Hereri, 2019; Abdulle, 1999; Ifrah Mohamud Magan, 2019; Kusow, 2006; Moret, Baglioni, & Efiñayí-mäder, 2006; Moret, Baglioni, & Efiñayí-Mäder, 2006; UN DESA, 2019). The language is the main challenge that Somalis experience in foreign countries. Another crucial challenge is the Somalis' multiple identities—Muslim, black and refugee; this leads to discrimination that Somalis face in their hosting countries.

Charting New Academic Horizons: the Future of Sociology in Somali Higher Education

Since the modern university's existence about 18th century onward, there have been conflicting stories on a university and its functions? Moreover, what goal does it aim to achieve? Since then, universities have been seen as a hub of communities

enthusiastic for studying and members' personal development, sources of professional personal and vocational identity, innovators and evaluators of new knowledge, and more importantly, contributors to the nation, society, and nations. Empirically, universities contributed to the positive construction of society through the generation of knowledge and morality. It also equips graduates with rational critical thinking. It prepares individuals that contribute to the formation of cohesive and tolerant communities.

Sociology is the study of society. It is crucial for understanding human interactions and beneficial both for people and the individual (OpenStax, 2019). Although it is late, This article argues that Somali universities need to employ sociology as a study discipline. In sociology, people study critical thinking about their problems and the issues that challenge society. Somalis face many problems in their living ways, such as tribalism, prolonged conflict, migration, terrorism and many others. While most Somali studies investigate those problems, most do not employ a sociological method. Instead, they engage in other fields of study such as economy, political science, etc. The limitation of sociological studies in Somalia extends the poor knowledge of those prolonging problems and developing suitable solutions.

Universities can be leading contributors for exploring, studying and overcoming the Somali problems through sociological training, which prepares intellectually with informed decisions. Somalia's decision to follow socialism can be the best example of how Somalis need sociological understanding. Somalia's adherence to socialism became official on the first anniversary of the

military coup when Siad Barre proclaimed that Somalia was a socialist state, despite the fact that the country had no history of class conflict in the Marxist sense (Metz, 1992, p. 40). The regime misled society with incorrect interpretations of Marxist ideology. For purposes of Marxist analysis, therefore, tribalism was equated with class in a society struggling to liberate itself from distinctions imposed by lineage group affiliation (Metz, 1992, p. 42).

At the time, Siad Barre explained that the official ideology consisted of three elements: his own conception of community development based on the principle of self-reliance, a form of socialism based on Marxist principles, and Islam (Metz, 1992, p. 42). These were subsumed under "scientific socialism," although such a definition was at variance with the Soviet and Chinese models to which reference was frequently made (Metz, 1992, p. 42). The regime's poor understanding of Marxist ideology caused the government to mix the Koran aspects with Marxist ideology. The theoretical underpinning of the state ideology combined aspects of the Quran with the influences of Marx, Lenin, Mao, and Mussolini, but Siad Barre was pragmatic in its application (Metz, 1992, p. 42). "Socialism is not a religion," he explained; "It is a political principle" to organize government and manage the production (Metz, 1992, p. 42).

Another similar example is how simply Somalia withdrew Socialist ideology. Following the war between Somalia and Ethiopia in 1977/1978, Somalia ceased its diplomatic relations with the Soviet Union; this uninformed decision ignited Somalia's defeat of the war and paved the way for the Somali civil. For all the rhetoric extolling scientific socialism, however, genuine Marxist sympathies were not deep-rooted in Somalia (Metz et al., 1993, p. 42). But the ideology was acknowledged--partly in view of the country's economic and military dependence on the Soviet Union--as the most convenient peg on which to hang a revolution introduced through a military coup that had supplanted a Western-oriented parliamentary democracy (Metz et al., 1993). This

article argues that, if there had been accurate sociological understanding, the Somali catastrophe could have been prevented. Thus, to avoid such devastating decisions, Somali universities urgently need to provide sociology to understand the changing world. Similarly, intellectuals equipped with sociological training can be a beacon of hope for studying daily challenges among the Somalis.

Sociological studies about the Somali people are limited with very narrow debates. The available sociological works are either written by foreigners or Somalis trained by foreigners. Thus, Somali universities can transform this gap into an opportunity by establishing a sociology department and training local students for a better future for their society. The availability of sociology in Somali universities will produce local intellectuals experiencing social facts about them instead of reading external sources. It is worth noting that foreigners lead Somali studies, and their studies' reality is questionable. The Somali universities can also fill this gap and become research hubs to lead Somali studies by providing missing fields of study, particularly sociology.

Conclusion

This article delves into the intricate tapestry of sociology as an academic discipline within Somali universities, uncovering both its historical roots and contemporary challenges. Our analysis, grounded in a Qualitative Descriptive Review, reveals that sociology in Somali higher education is not just a subject; it is a lens through which the complex social dynamics of post-colonial Somalia can be understood and addressed. The emergence of sociology in this context is marked by a blend of traditional societal values and modern academic principles, offering a unique perspective on social issues.

The absence of sociology in earlier educational frameworks in Somalia has left a noticeable gap in understanding social structures and dynamics. However, the recent integration of sociology into university curricula signifies a promising shift towards a more holistic educational approach. This integration is not without its challenges, including resource limitations and the need for culturally relevant sociological curricula, but it paves the way for a more nuanced understanding of Somali society.

The implications of this study extend beyond academia. By fostering critical thinking and social awareness, sociology equips students to become agents of change, capable of addressing societal issues such as clan conflicts, migration, and gender dynamics. Moreover, the development of sociology in Somali universities can serve as a model for other post-conflict nations striving to rebuild their educational systems with a focus on social sciences.

In conclusion, the study reaffirms the critical role of sociology in shaping a comprehensive and relevant higher education system in Somalia. It calls for continued investment in academic resources, research, and curriculum development to nurture this budding discipline. Future research should aim to bridge the gap between sociological theory and practice, ensuring that the study of sociology remains dynamically aligned with the evolving fabric of Somali society.

References

- Abdi, A. A. (1998). Education in Somalia: History, destruction, and calls for reconstruction. *Comparative Education*, 34(3), 327–340.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03050069828171>

- Hereri, A. (2019). Interview with Somali ambassador to Turkey. Universal TV. Retrieved from <https://youtu.be/hGWPXDWceCc>
- Abdulle, M. H. (1999). *Somali immigrants in Ottawa: The causes of their migration and the challenges of resettling in Canada*. University of Ottawa.
- Abdulle, M. H., Moret, J., Baglioni, S., Efionayi-mäder, D., Paçacı Elitok, S., & Straubhaar, T. (2012). *Somali immigrants in Ottawa: The causes of their migration and the challenges of resettling in Canada*. In SFM Studies. Hamburg: Hamburg University Press.
- Bade, Z. A. (2020). Dynamics of Religion and Nationalism in Somalia: Allies and Opponents. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Researches*, 7, 38–54.
- Bade, Z. A., & Hared, A. A. (2021). Understanding Somali Conflict: Causes, Consequences and Strategies for Peace-Building. *Developing Country Studies*, 11(3), 46–57. <https://doi.org/10.7176/dcs/11-3-05>
- Behr, A. W. (2018). Identity and Body Borders: The Perception of the Kenya Somalia Border. *American Journal of International Relations*, 3(1), 1–10.
- Besnard, P. (1983). The Durkheimians and the Founding of French Sociology. In *Sociological Domain*.
- Cooley, C. H. (1920). Reflections upon the sociology of Herbert Spencer. In *American Journal of Sociology*. University of Chicago Press.
- Diriye, O. (2019). *Research Partnership Between Universities: A Missing Link in Turkey-Somalia Relationship*.
- Eno, M. A. (2008). *The Bantu-Jareer Somalis: Unearthing Apartheid in the Horn of Africa*. Adonis & Abbey Pub Ltd.
- Eno, M. A., & Kusow, A. M. (2014). Racial and caste Prejudice in Somalia. *Journal of Somali Studies*, 1(2), 91–118.
- Ferrante-Wallace, J. (2013). *Sociology: A Global Perspective*. Cengage Learning.
- Hammond, R., Cheney, P., & Pearsey, R. (2015). *Introduction to sociology*. Rocky Ridge Press.
- Magan, I.M.. (2019). On Being Black, Muslim, and a Refugee: Stories of Somalis in Chicago. *Journal of Immigrant and Refugee Studies*, 18(2), 172–188. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15562948.2019.1617451>
- Ingiriis, M. H. (2020). *The anthropology and sociology of the Somali diaspora - Cawo M. Abdi, Elusive Jannah: the Somali diaspora and a borderless Muslim identity*. Minneapolis MN: University of Minnesota Press.
- Jacoby, H. (1976). *The Bureaucratization of the world (Translated by Eveline Kanes)*. University of California Press. London.
- Jowi, J. O., Obamba, M., Schoole, C., Barifaijo, M., Oanda, O., & Alabi, G. (2013). Governance of higher education, research and innovation in Ghana, Kenya and Uganda. Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com/document/445775018/Governance-of-higher-education-research-and-innovation-in-Ghana-Kenya-and-Uganda>
- Kusow, A. M. (2004). Contested Narratives and the Crisis of the Nation-State in Somalia: A prolegomenon. In *Putting the Cart before the Horse: Contested Narratives and the Crisis of the Nation State in Somalia*.

- Kusow, A. M. (2006). Migration and racial formations among Somali immigrants in North America. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 32(3), 533–551. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691830600555079>
- Marshall, G., & Scott, J. (1998). *A dictionary of sociology*. Oxford University Press Oxford.
- Metz, H. C. (1992). *Somalia: A Country Study*. GPO for the Library of Congress. Retrieved from <http://countrystudies.us/somalia/44.htm>
- Metz, H. C., Congress., L. of, Division., F. R., & Section), T. L. K. C. (Library of C. H. (1993). *Somalia: a country study*. Federal Research Division, Library of Congress : For sale by the Supt. of Docs., U.S. G.P.O.
- Moret, J., Baglioni, S., & Efiionayi-mäder, D. (2006). *The Path of Somali Refugees into Exile: A Comparative Analysis of Secondary Movements and Policy Responses*. SFM Studies.
- Moret, J., Baglioni, S., & Efiionayi-Mäder, D. (2006). *The path of Somali refugees into exile. A comparative analysis of secondary movements and policy responses*. SFM Studies.
- OpenStax, C. (2019). *Introduction To Sociology*. 1st Canadian Edition.
- Pestalozza, L. (1974). *The Somalian Revolution*. Editions Afrique Asie Amérique latine.
- Ritzer, G. (2011). *Sociological theory*, eight edition. In New York, America: The McGraw-Hill Companies. McGraw Hill.
- Royce, E. (2015). *Classical social theory and modern society: Marx, Durkheim, Weber*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Samatar, A. I. (2006). Debating Somali identity in a British tribunal: the case of the BBC Somali Service. *The Arab World Geographer*, 9(1), 40–73.
- Sawyerr, A. (2004). Challenges facing African universities: Selected issues. *African Studies Review*, 47(1), 1–59. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0002020600026986>
- Sheik-Abdi, A. (1981). Ideology and leadership in Somalia. *The Journal of Modern African Studies*, 19(1), 163–172. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/S0022278X00054161>
- Taylor, A. C. M., Universities., I. A. of, & Bureau., I. U. (1993). *International handbook of universities*. Stockton Press ; IAU Press.
- UN DESA. (2019). International Migrant Stock 2019: Country Profile Somalia. Retrieved from https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/data/estimates2/docs/MigrationStockDocumentation_2019.pdf